

Ontology and Grammar of the SOPHIE Choreography Conceptual Framework - An Ontological Model for Knowledge Management

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Abstract: Ontologies have been recognized as a fundamental infrastructure for advanced approaches to Knowledge Management (KM) automation in SOA. Building services communicate with each other by exchanging self-contained messages. Depending on the specific requirements of the business model they serve and the application domain for which services were deployed, a number of mismatches (i.e. sequence and cardinality of messages exchanges, structure and format of messages and content semantics), can occur which prevent interoperation among a prior compatible services. Existing choreography technologies attempt to model such external visible behavior. However, they lack the consistent semantic support required to fully meet the necessities of heterogeneous KM environments. This paper describes the ontology and grammar of **SOPHIE**, a semantic service-based choreography framework for overcoming conversational pattern mismatches in knowledge intensive environments. Consequently, the paper provides an overview of the framework that depicts its main building blocks, so a good understanding of the ontology and grammar that summarize the conceptual model is gained. Such ontology allows the design and description of fully fledged choreographies that can be used, as a result of a mediation task, to produce the mediating structures that in fact allow dynamic service-to-service interoperation. Finally, a use case centred in the telecommunications field serves as proof of concept of how **SOPHIE** is being applied.

Keywords: Semantic Services, Choreography

Categories: H.3.1, H.3.2, H.3.3, H.3.7, H.5.1

1 Introduction

The discipline of Knowledge Management (KM) has evolved and matured in the last decade, resulting in a considerable amount of models, tools and technologies [Sicilia06]. Nonetheless, such conceptual structures should be properly integrated into existing ontological bases, for the practical purpose of providing the required support for the development of intelligent applications. In addition, the supporting technologies for socialization, externalization, combination and internalization of knowledge are available and can be applied to build KM solutions of a diverse kind [Mohame04]. Formal ontologies [Gruber93] have been proposed and applied as the backbone of KM systems [Maedche03], and even ontologies specific to certain KM domains exist—e.g. for software development organizations [Marwick01]. The new requirements in the design of knowledge [Sicilia06] intensive software systems call

for well decoupled approaches where components interoperate by exchanging self-contained messages. These systems realize their functionality by defining from a high-level point of view their dynamics. Still, components autonomously define their control flow and the message interface that allows others consuming their functionality. As the use of services is catching up, more and more interest is being placed in the development of initiatives that allow their agile interoperation. With the aim of fulfilling the communication necessities, the concept of choreography, as a means to model the external visible behaviour of services within KM environments has been sketched.

Services communicate with each other by exchanging self-contained messages, allowing them to make or to respond to requests. Upon the reception of a message, services react by executing some internal processes and possibly responding with other messages. Depending on the specific requirements of the business model they serve and the application domain for which services were deployed, a number of mismatches can occur which prevent interoperation among a prior compatible services.

- **Sequence and cardinality of messages exchanges.** Services follow different conversational patterns, which define the order and number in which messages are sent and/or received in a univocal way. A number of scenarios can be sketched that prevent interoperation:
 1. Messages being sent/received in a different order than expected (Sequence).
 2. Too many messages being sent/received that are not compliant with the expected behavior of the other party –i.e. acks, control messages, or messages being split into smaller ones– (Cardinality).
 3. Too little messages are sent/received not being compliant with the expected behavior of the other party –one message that makes up for a number of others, or no acks or no control messages– (Cardinality).
- **Structure and format of messages.** Services use different conceptualizations and naming conventions for encoding contents and characterizing messages. Even when all the information expected is enclosed in messages, the means to assert compatibility, identify and reorganize the contents and structure of messages and rename messages as appropriate, so they match the conversational model of the receiving party, need to be put in place.
- **Content Semantics.** Depending on the application domain services make use of a wide range of terminological conventions to represent concepts encoded into messages and the messages themselves. Prior to effective message exchanges the means to identify equivalent concepts needs to be put in place so messages and the pieces of data they contain can be understood by interacting services.

Due to the fact that the semantics, sequence, cardinality, structure and format followed by interacting services is wide, the means to overcome these limitations need to be put in place. Current infrastructures present an “ad-hoc” alternative for

overcoming heterogeneity which need to be improved so services are enabled to interact in a more dynamic and decoupled fashion.

SOPHIE^{1,2} ([Arroyo, 06a][Arroyo, 06b]), puts in place the required computational semantics that enable defining a mediation layer among the message exchanges of heterogeneous Semantic Services in knowledge intensive environments. This is achieved regardless of the structural and behavioural models and the technological aspects used by interacting parties.

The remaining of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 shows a high level architecture of the framework, together with the main actors involved and core ideas behind the framework. Section 3 presents the ontology of the conceptual framework that summarizes the main concepts required to model fully-fledged choreographies, providing. Section 4 Section 4 introduces the grammar of the **SOPHIE** choreography framework. Section 5 depicts the details of a use case centred in the Telecommunication industry where the principles and ideas of SOPHIE have been successfully applied. Finally, Section 6 outlines the conclusion of this research together with future direction for extending the work.

Figure 1: Choreography service

2 SOPHIE

SOPHIE is a knowledge management conceptual framework and architecture for a choreography service realized as a SOA. Services that use the choreography service fall into two main categories, namely, initiating parties and answering services. Both parties produce and consume messages. Additionally, initiating parties indicate the

¹ **SOPHIE** is an acronym for Semantic services chOreograPHi servIce

² Notice that this paper complements a series of papers already published that go in detail into various aspects of the framework. This is why, only the relevant characteristics of **SOPHIE** are briefly covered in this work. The interested reader is encouraged to read other **SOPHIE** related publications to gain a deeper understanding of its particularities and details.

choreography framework by means of any of its constitutes correlating services that the infrastructure for the interoperation of heterogeneous message exchanges should be established.

Figure 1 shows a high level architecture of the conceptual framework. Informally, initiating parties indicate that want to communicate with an answering service by means of “*generateOperationalModel*” (1). Once an operational model that allows the interoperation among the heterogeneous message exchanges has been created, parties can start submitting messages by means of the “*correlateMessage*” (2) primitive. Messages will go through the designated operational model, forwarding the framework the message(s) to the receiving party according to its choreography. Finally, when the conversation is finished, either party indicates that the operational model for a given conversation can be put off line, by means of the primitive “*removeOperationalModel*”.

3.1 Conversations

A *conversation* represents the logical entity that permits to group a set of related message exchanges among parties. Conversations are composed of a number of building blocks.

Elements represent elementary unit of data that build up *documents*. Documents are complete, self-contained groups of elements that are transmitted over the wire within *messages*. Messages characterize the primitive piece of data that can be exchanged among parties. As messages are exchanged, a variety of recurrent scenarios can be played out. *Message Exchange Patterns (MEP)*, identify placeholders for messages, that allow to model its sequence and cardinality, defining the order on which parties send a receive messages. A set of messages sent and received among parties, optionally following Message Exchanged Patterns are referred as *message exchange*. They characterize a well defined part of a conversation. A *conversation* can be thus defined as a set of message exchanges among parties with the aim of fulfilling some goal. Every conversation need to rely on top of some communication facility referred as *communication network*.

3.2 Choreographies

A *choreography* describes the behavior of the answering service from the initiating party point of view [Roman04a]. It governs the message exchanges among parties in a conversation. A choreography as presented in this work is based on the Finite State Machines (FSMs)³ formalism. FSMs allow specifying the sequences of states the choreography goes through during its lifetime, together with its responses to events. In this sense the main building blocks of abstract state machines are up to some extent redraw.

A *state* is a situation during the lifetime of a choreography during which it waits for some event or satisfies some condition. Conditions are modeled as *booleanExpression*. Boolean expressions are expressions evaluated to “*true*” or

³ Activities, entry actions and exit actions have been deliberately left out of the scope of the work, as they are not required for purpose of the thesis.

“*false*” as in any programming or ontology language. An action represents the atomic task of sending a message to a party. *Events* represent occurrences of stimulus. They do not specify state transitions. Transitions among states are defined by *guarded transitions*. Guarded transitions allow modeling the relations between two states by means of *events*, *actions* and *guard conditions*. Guarded conditions are rules that specify a target state. *Parts* permit to relate guarded transitions and message exchanges, defining the message exchange in terms of state transitions. Finally, a choreography comprises a set of parts that define a conversation.

3.3 Logic Boxes

The atomic building blocks that permit to solve the mismatches among interacting parties are referred as *logic boxes*. A logic box facilitates the means to reorganize the content of documents, its mapping to messages, and the order and cardinality of messages, enabling the interoperation among heterogeneous message exchanges. Additionally, and depending on the type of box, the differences in the vocabulary used to describe the application domain can be overcome. Currently the specification defines five different types of logic boxes, namely: *refiner box*, *merge box*, *split box*, *select box*, *add box*. Logic boxes are grouped into *logic diagrams*. Logic diagrams permit to model the relation among the message exchange pattern followed by the initiating party, and the one used by the answering service. Logic diagrams are assimilated, for implementation purposes, to *correspondence tables*. A correspondence table is a logical structure, similar to routing tables, which defines relations among incoming and outgoing messages as a realization of a logic diagram. A number of logic diagrams defining a conversation are referred as *logic group*.

3.4 Ontologies

Ontologies define the semantics of the framework. They facilitate a formal and consensual [Gruber93] vocabulary as data and information machine-processable semantics for the shared and common understanding of a domain [Fensel01] that can be mediated for the understanding of interacting parties. *Domain ontologies* supply the general vocabulary to describe the application domain of parties. *Choreography ontologies* make available the terminology that describes the choreography of parties. In doing so they define the different entities (concepts) taking part in a choreography. *Ontology mappings* characterize the conceptual entity that allows to link similar ontological concepts and instances.

3.5 Related Technologies

In the following different technologies that are related to the definition of a conceptual framework for choreography are concisely reviewed. In doing so, their core characteristics are presented, their drawbacks identified and the main ideas reused in this research are summarized.

		<i>layered model</i>		
		<i>no</i>		<i>yes</i>
<i>relation with communication framework</i>	<i>tight</i>	Business Process Languages	Choreography Languages	
	<i>loose</i>	Choreography Languages	Semantic-driven choreography initiatives	SOPHIE
		<i>no</i>	<i>yes</i>	
		<i>semantic support</i>		

Table 1: *A first cut in classifying related languages*

Table 1 presents a preliminary classification based on a three dimension exam. The first dimension depicts the relation with the underlying communication framework, differentiating among tight and loose. The second one addresses the semantic support provided. Finally, the third one discriminates them depending on whether or not they follow a layered model. Based on these depiction four main categories of languages are distinguished:

- Technologies with a tight relation to the underlying communication framework, lacking of a layered model and no support for semantics, such as BPEL4WS
- Technologies with a tight relation to the underlying communication framework, that follow a layered model and no support for semantics, such as WS-CDL
- Technologies with a loose relation to the underlying communication framework, lacking of a layered model and no support for semantics, such as WSCI
- Technologies with a loose relation to the underlying communication framework, with support for semantics but lacking of a layered model, such as WSMO-Choreography

In [Arroyo06b] a detailed overview of the related languages detailed in Table 1 is presented.

4 Ontology of the Conceptual Model

In the following the ontology that summarizes the ideas and concepts of SOPHIE is presented. In doing so, the different conceptual models are briefly reviewed and the fragments of the ontology where such concepts are modeled are provided.

4.1 Conceptual Model

The conceptual model presented of **SOPHIE** describes the structure, behavior, operation and ontologies of conceptual framework for choreography as separate concerns. The semantic model details the semantic support. The structural concern provides the grounding pillars of the framework. The behavioral concern permits to model the conduct of the structural model. Finally, the operational concern facilitates the means to allow the interoperation of different behavioral models.

This clear separation of concerns facilitates a straight mechanism to extend the different models, for example Petri nets, temporal logic or transaction logic can be used instead of Finite State Machines (FSMs) for the behavioral model.

The work presented here defines the behavioral model as FSMs. Still, any other suitable paradigm can be easily plugged-in. The terms used, in particular the terms choreography, state and guarded transition, follow the formalism proposed in [Roman04b] and [Booch99]. Furthermore, the semantic model is currently based on WSMML. Nonetheless, the design allows to easily extending the grammar and ontology of **SOPHIE** to accommodate any other ontology language.

```

wsmIVariant _"http://www.wsmo.org/wsmml/wsmml-syntax/wsmml-flight"

namespace {
    _"http://www.example.org/ontologies/sophie#",
    dc _"http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1#",
    xsd _"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#",
    wsmml _"http://www.wsmo.org/wsmml-syntax#"
}

ontology _"http://www.deri.org/ontology/sophie#"

nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#title hasValue "Choreography Conceptual Model"
    dc#creator hasValue "Sinuhé Arroyo"
    dc#description hasValue "an ontology for describing the concepts of
        SOPHIE"
    dc#publisher hasValue "DERI International"
    dc#contributor hasValue "Jos de Bruijn"
    dc#date hasValue "2005-04-11"
    dc#type hasValue "http://www.deri.org/2005/#ontology"
    dc#format hasValue "text/html"
    dc#language hasValue "en-us"
    dc#rights hasValue "http://deri.at/privacy.html"
    version hasValue "$Revision 0.1$"
endNonFunctionalProperties

concept sophie#conceptualModel
    nonFunctionalProperties
        dc#description hasValue "root of the conceptual model"
    endNonFunctionalProperties

```

structuralConcern ofType (0 1) structural
behavioralConcern ofType (0 1) behavioral
operationalConcern ofType (0 1) operational
ontologies ofType (0 1) sophie#ontologies

concept *sophie#entity*

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description hasValue "entities of the choreography service"

endNonFunctionalProperties

name ofType (1 1) sophie#name

URI ofType (1 1) sophie#uri

concept *sophie#name*

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description hasValue "name or key value of an entity"

endNonFunctionalProperties

concept *sophie#handler*

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description hasValue "address and protocol of an entity"

endNonFunctionalProperties

concept *sophie#uri*

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description hasValue "handler, entity and identifier"

endNonFunctionalProperties

handler ofType (1 1) sophie#handler

entity ofType (1 1) sophie#entityType

identifier ofType (1 1) sophie#name

concept *sophie#entityType*

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description hasValue "type of an entity"

endNonFunctionalProperties

axiom *sophie#allowedEntityTypes*

definedBy

!- ?x memberOf entityType and naf ?x = sophie#party

and naf ?x = sophie#element

and naf ?x = sophie#document

and naf ?x = sophie#message

and naf ?x = sophie#mep

and naf ?x = sophie#messageExchange

and naf ?x = sophie#conversation

and naf ?x = sophie#state

and naf ?x = sophie#action

```

and naf ?x = sophie#booleanExpression
and naf ?x = sophie#event
and naf ?x = sophie#guardCondition
and naf ?x = sophie#guardedTransition
and naf ?x = sophie#part
and naf ?x = sophie#choreography
and naf ?x = sophie#logicBox
and naf ?x = sophie#logicDiagram
and naf ?x = sophie#logicGroup
and naf ?x = sophie#correspondenceTable
and naf ?x = sophie#correspondenceModel
and naf ?x = sophie#domainOntology
and naf ?x = sophie#choreographyModel
and naf ?x = sophie#choreographyOntology
and naf ?x = sophie#ontologyMapping.

```

```

concept sophie#role

```

```

nonFunctionalProperties

```

```

  dc#description hasValue "specifies whether a party is an initiating
    party an answering service or a correlating
    service"

```

```

endNonFunctionalProperties

```

```

axiom sophie#allowedRoles

```

```

definedBy

```

```

  !- ?x memberOf role and naf ?x = sophie# initiatingParty
    and naf ?x = sophie# answeringService
    and naf ?x = sophie# correlatingService.

```

```

concept sophie#formalism

```

```

nonFunctionalProperties

```

```

  dc#description hasValue "formalism"

```

```

endNonFunctionalProperties

```

```

concept sophie#concern

```

```

nonFunctionalProperties

```

```

  dc#description hasValue "model of the choreography service "

```

```

endNonFunctionalProperties

```

4.1.1 Structural Model

The structural model deals with the provision of a reusable collection of entities following different levels of abstraction that facilitate the basis for the description of a conceptual model. Table 2, enumerates the entities that allow the structural model to be defined.

<i>element</i> = [name, type, value]
<i>document</i> = [name, URI, elements* ⁴]
<i>message</i> = [name, URI, from ⁵ , to [?] , documents*]
<i>messageExchangePattern</i> = [name, URI, description [?]]
<i>message exchange</i> = [name, URI, mep [?] , messages*]
<i>conversation</i> = [name, URI, messageExchanges*]

Table 2: Structural model

Conversations are the outer most entity of the structural model. They represent the logical entity that permits to group a set of related message exchanges among parties. Conversations are composed of a set of building blocks. *Elements* describe elementary units of data that define a name, a type⁶ and a value that build documents. Documents are complete, self-contained groups of elements. Documents are transmitted over the wire within *messages*. Messages characterize pieces of information that can be exchanged among parties. As messages are exchanged, a variety of recurrent scenarios can be played out as defined by *Message Exchange Patterns (MEP)*. A MEP defines a minimal contract among parties. They allow the sequence and cardinality of messages to be modeled, defining the order in which parties send and receive messages. The constituent *description* is a *part* that depicts the behavior of the pattern. A set of messages sent and received among parties optionally following a Message Exchanged Pattern that account for a well defined part of a conversation, is referred as a *message exchange*. A *conversation* can thus be defined as a set of message exchanges among parties, optionally following message exchange patterns to model their behavior. Every conversation need to rely on top of some communication facility, referred to as a *communication network*.

```

concept sophie#structural
  subConceptOf {concern}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "structural model"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  formalisms ofType (0 *) sophie#formalism

```

```

axiom sophie#allowedStructuralFormalisms
  definedBy
    !- ?x memberOf entityType and naf ?x = sophie#MEPConversational.

```

```

concept sophie#MEPConversational
  subConceptOf {formalism}

```

⁴ The symbol "*" represents that there can exist zero or more instances of the attribute

⁵ The symbol "?" represents zero or one instances of the attribute

⁶ Element types, belong to a limited set of types as defined by the standard XSD [Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.]

nonFunctionalProperties*dc#description hasValue "MEP structural formalism"***endNonFunctionalProperties***party ofType (1 1) sophie#party**elements ofType (0 *) sophie#element**documents ofType (0 *) sophie#document**messages ofType (0 *) sophie#message**messageExchanges ofType (0 *) sophie#messageExchange**MEPs ofType (0 *) sophie#mep**conversations ofType (0 *) sophie#conversation**sufficientElements ofType (0 *) sophie#sufficientSet**sufficientMessages ofType (0 *) sophie#sufficientSet***concept sophie#type****nonFunctionalProperties***dc#description hasValue "XSD type subset"***endNonFunctionalProperties****axiom sophie#allowedTypes****definedBy**

*!- ?x memberOf type and naf ?x = xsd#string
 and naf ?x = xsd#decimal
 and naf ?x = xsd#integer
 and naf ?x = xsd#float
 and naf ?x = xsd#boolean
 and naf ?x = xsd#date
 and naf ?x = xsd#time.*

concept sophie#value**nonFunctionalProperties***dc#description hasValue "value of the element"***endNonFunctionalProperties***representation ofType _string**type ofType sophie#type***concept sophie#element****subConceptOf {entity}****nonFunctionalProperties***dc#description hasValue "piece of data either supplied or consumed
by parties"***endNonFunctionalProperties***sophie#value ofType (1 1) sophie#value***concept sophie#sufficientSet****subConceptOf {entity}****nonFunctionalProperties**

dc#description hasValue "sufficient set of entities"
endNonFunctionalProperties
*entities ofType (0 *) sophie#entity*
sophie#hasValue ofType (1 1) sophie#value

concept *sophie#party*
subConceptOf {sophie#entity}
nonFunctionalProperties
dc#description hasValue "active entities inside or outside the choreography framework"
endNonFunctionalProperties
role ofType (1 1) sophie#role
URI ofType (1 1) sophie#role

concept *sophie#document*
subConceptOf {entity}
nonFunctionalProperties
dc#description hasValue "grouping of a number related elements"
endNonFunctionalProperties
*elements ofType (0 *) sophie#element*

concept *sophie#message*
subConceptOf {entity}
nonFunctionalProperties
dc#description hasValue "minimal unit that can be exchanged among parties"
endNonFunctionalProperties
from ofType (0 1) sophie#party
to ofType (0 1) sophie#party
*documents ofType (0 *) sophie#document*

concept *sophie#mep*
subConceptOf {entity}
nonFunctionalProperties
dc#description hasValue "placeholder for message exchanges"
endNonFunctionalProperties
description ofType (0 1) sophie#part

concept *sophie#messageExchange*
subConceptOf {entity}
nonFunctionalProperties
dc#description hasValue "piece of a conversation optionally following a mep"
endNonFunctionalProperties
MEP ofType (0 1) sophie#mep
*messages ofType (0 *) sophie#message*

```

concept sophie#conversation
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "set of message exchanges"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  messageExchanges ofType (0 *) sophie#messageExchange

```

4.1.2 Behavioral Model

The behavioral model cares for the description of the dynamic interaction among the entities defined in the structural model. As presented in this work, the behavioral models are based on the formalism presented by Finite State Machines (FSMs) [Wagner06]. Nevertheless, any other formalism such as Petri nets, temporal or transactional logic can be easily modeled and plugged-in in to the behavioral model. In doing so, it makes use of the entities enumerated in Table 3.

<i>booleanExpression</i> = [name, URI, <i>expression</i> [?]]
<i>state</i> = [name, URI, <i>subStates</i> *]
<i>action</i> = [name, URI, <i>task</i> [?]]
<i>task</i> = [party, message]
<i>event</i> = [name, URI, <i>booleanExpression</i> [?]]
<i>guardCondition</i> = [name, URI, <i>rule</i> [?]]
<i>rule</i> = [if <i>booleanExpression</i> then <i>state</i>]
<i>guarded transition</i> = [name, URI, <i>events</i> *, <i>guardCondition</i> [?] , <i>actions</i> *]
<i>part</i> = [name, URI, <i>messageExchange</i> [?] , <i>guardedTransitions</i> *]
<i>choreography</i> = [name, URI, <i>conversation</i> [?] , <i>parts</i> *]

Table 3: Behavioral model

A *choreography* represents the outer most entity in the behavioral model. It describes the behavior of the answering service from the initiating party point's of view [Roman04a]. It governs the message exchanges among parties in a conversation.

States, *actions* and *events* and *guard conditions* represent the same concepts as defined by FSMs. However, the scope of events and actions has been narrowed. Particularly, actions represent the atomic task of sending a message, and events can not trigger a state transition, since do not specify a target state, but just a *booleanExpression*. Additionally, activities, entry actions and exit actions have been deliberately left out of the scope of the work, as they are not required for our purposes. Finally, the concept of guarded transitions, parts and choreography have been added.

A *guarded transition* defines the relationship between states by means of events, guard conditions and actions. In a nutshell, a guarded transition defines events and conditions, which when satisfied, perform certain actions and trigger the state transition as defined in the guarded condition. *Parts* permit guarded transitions and message exchanges to be related, defining the message exchange in terms of state transitions according to the logic of the application. Finally, a *choreography* can be

defined as a set of parts, which govern the message exchanges among parties in a conversation.

```

concept sophie#behavioral
  subConceptOf {concern}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "behavioral model"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  hasFormalism ofType (0 *) sophie#formalism

axiom sophie#allowedBehavioralFormalisms
  definedBy
    !- ?x memberOf entityType and naf ?x = sophie#FSM.

concept sophie#FSM
  subConceptOf {formalism}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "Finite State Machine behavioral formalism"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  states ofType (0 *) sophie#state
  actions ofType (0 *) sophie#action
  booleanExpressions ofType (0 *) sophie#booleanExpression
  events ofType (0 *) sophie#event
  guardConditions ofType (0 *) sophie#guardCondition
  guardTransitions ofType (0 *) sophie#guardTransition
  parts ofType (0 *) sophie#part
  choreography ofType (0 1) sophie#choreography
  sufficientActions ofType (0 *) sophie#sufficientSet
  sufficientBooleanExpressions ofType (0 *) sophie#sufficientSet

concept sophie#state
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "condition or situation during the lifetime of a
    choreography"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  subStates ofType (0 *) sophie#state

concept sophie#task
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "Party and message to be sent"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  party ofType (0 1) sophie#party
  message ofType (0 1) sophie#message

```

```

concept sophie#action
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "action of sending a message"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  task ofType (0 1) sophie#task

concept sophie#booleanExpression
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "boolean expression"
  endNonFunctionalProperties

concept sophie#event
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "occurrence of an stimulus that has a location
    in time and space"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  booleanExpression ofType (0 1) sophie#booleanExpression

concept sophie#rule
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "defines a rule"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  booleanExpression ofType (0 1) sophie#booleanExpression
  state ofType (0 1) sophie#state

concept sophie#guardCondition
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "defines transitions among states by means of
    rules"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  rule ofType (0 1) sophie#rule

concept sophie#guardTransition
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "defines relations among states by means of
    events, guardConditions and actions"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  events ofType (0 *) event
  guardCondition ofType (0 1) sophie#guardCondition
  actions ofType (1 *) sophie#action

```

```

concept sophie#part
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "allows establishing the link among a set of
      guarded transitions and a message
      exchange"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  messageExchange ofType (0 1) sophie#messageExchange
  guardTransitions ofType (0 *) sophie#guardTransition

concept sophie#choreography
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "set of parts that govern the message
      exchange among parties in a conversation"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  hasConversation ofType (0 1) sophie#conversation
  hasParts ofType (0 *) sophie#part

```

4.1.3 Operational Model

The operational model facilitates the means to allow the interoperation among different behavioral models. Table 4, enumerates the entities that allow an operational model to be defined.

<pre> logicBox = [name, URI, type, inputMessages*, inputMep?, outputMep?, ontologyMapping?] logicDiagram = [name, URI, inputMessageExchange?, outputMessageExchange?, logicBoxes*] logicGroup = [name, URI, conversation?, logicDiagrams*] </pre>

Table 4: Entities of the operational model

Logic boxes constitute the key entity of the operational model. The outer most entities of the operational model are logic groups.

```

concept sophie#operational
  subConceptOf {concern}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "operational model"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  formalism ofType (0 *) sophie#formalism

axiom sophie#allowedOperationalFormalisms
  definedBy
    !- ?x memberOf entityType and naf ?x = sophie#FSM.

```

```

concept sophie#logicBoxCorrespondence
  subConceptOf {formalism}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "Logic box behavioral formalism"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  logicBoxes ofType (0 *) sophie#logicBox
  logicDiagrams ofType (0 *) sophie#logicDiagram
  logicGroups ofType (0 *) sophie#logicGroup
  correspondenceTables ofType (0 *) sophie#correspondenceTable
  correspondenceModels ofType (0 *) sophie#correspondenceModel

concept sophie#logicBoxType
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "type of the logic box "
  endNonFunctionalProperties

axiom sophie#allowedBoxTypes
  definedBy
    !- ?x memberOf logicBoxType and naf ?x = sophie#refineBox
      and naf ?x = sophie#mergeBox
      and naf ?x = sophie#splitBox
      and naf ?x = sophie#selectBox
      and naf ?x = sophie#addBox.

concept sophie#logicBox
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "allows to solve a number of heterogeneities
      in the messages exchanged by parties"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  type ofType (1 1) sophie#logicBoxType
  inputMessages ofType (0 *) sophie#message
  inputMEP ofType (0 1) sophie#mep
  outputMep ofType (0 1) sophie#mep
  ontologyMapping ofType (0 1) sophie#ontologyMapping

concept sophie#logicDiagram
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "set of interconnected logic boxes that model
      the relation among the message exchanges
      used by interacting parties"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  inputMessageExchange ofType (0 1) sophie#messageExchange

```

outputMessageExchange **ofType** (0 1) *sophie#messageExchange*
logicBoxes **ofType** (0 *) *sophie#logicBox*

concept *sophie#logicGroup*

subConceptOf {entity}

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description **hasValue** "conceptual entity that allows to put together
a number of logic diagrams that model a
conversation"

endNonFunctionalProperties

conversation **ofType** (0 1) *sophie#conversation*

logicDiagrams **ofType** (0 *) *sophie#logicDiagram*

concept *sophie#correspondenceTable*

subConceptOf {entity}

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description **hasValue** "structure containing the operational model"

endNonFunctionalProperties

inputMessages **ofType** (0 *) *sophie#message*

outputMessages **ofType** (0 *) *sophie#message*

sophie#value **ofType** (0 *) *sophie#value*

concept *sophie#correspondenceModel*

subConceptOf {entity}

nonFunctionalProperties

dc#description **hasValue** "disjunctive piece of the operational model"

endNonFunctionalProperties

initiatingPartyCorrespondenceTable **ofType** (0 1)

sophie#correspondenceTable

answeringServiceCorrespondenceTable **ofType** (0 1)

sophie#correspondenceTable

4.1.4 Ontologies

The framework differentiates among three types of ontologies, namely “*domain ontologies*”, “*choreography model*” “*choreography ontologies*”. Domain ontologies facilitate the general vocabulary to describe the application domain of the parties. The choreography model summarizes the SOPHIE concepts and ideas as presented in this research. Finally, choreography ontologies provide the conceptual framework and vocabulary required to semantically describe a choreography, by borrowing terminology from the domain ontology and choreography model. Additionally *ontology mappings* put in place the mechanisms to link similar ontological concepts and instances, same for the domain and choreography ontologies.

<i>domainOntology = [name, URI]</i>
<i>choreographyOntology = [name, URI]</i>
<i>ontologyMapping = [name, URI, source, target]</i>

Table 5: Entities of the semantic model

Table 5, distinguishes the different constituents of the semantic model.

```

concept sophie#semantics
  subConceptOf {aspect}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "semantic aspects"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  hasSemanticModel ofType (0 1) sophie#semantic

concept sophie#semantic
  subConceptOf {model}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "semantic model"
  endNonFunctionalProperties

concept sophie#domainMapping
  subConceptOf {formalism}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "Domain knowledge mapping formalist formalism"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
  hasDomainOntologies ofType (0 *) sophie#domainOntology
  hasChoreographyOntologies ofType (0 *) sophie#choreographyOntology
  hasChoreographyMapping ofType (0 *) sophie#ontologyMapping

concept sophie#ontology
  subConceptOf {entity}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "ontology"
  endNonFunctionalProperties

concept sophie#domainOntology
  subConceptOf {sophie#ontology}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "domain ontology"
  endNonFunctionalProperties

concept sophie#choreographyOntology
  subConceptOf {sophie#ontology}
  nonFunctionalProperties

```

```

    dc#description hasValue "choreography ontology"
  endNonFunctionalProperties

```

```

concept sophie#ontologyMapping
  subConceptOf {sophie#ontology}
  nonFunctionalProperties
    dc#description hasValue "domain or choreography ontology mapping"
  endNonFunctionalProperties
    hasSource ofType (0 *) sophie#ontology
    hasTarget ofType (0 *) sophie#ontology

```

5 Grammar of the Conceptual Model

A symbol between square brackets ([]) is not required to occur (may occur zero or one time). A symbol between curly brackets is not required and may occur zero or more times. A symbol not enclosed in square or curly brackets is required and may only occur one time. The bar (|) stands for an exclusive choice. All keywords are represented in boldface. [de Bruijn04].

```

conceptualModel ::= 'ConceptualModel (' structure behavior operation
                                semantics ')
party ::= 'Party (' name URI role ')
name ::= identifier
URI7 ::= handler '/' entity '/' identifier
handler ::= identifier
entity ::= 'party' | 'element' | 'document' | 'message' | 'mep' | 'messageExchange' |
            'conversation' | 'state' | 'action' | 'booleanExpression' | 'event' |
            'guardCondition' | 'guardedTransition' | 'part' | 'choreography' |
            'logicBox' | 'logicDiagram' | 'logicGroup' | 'correspondenceTable' |
            'correspondenceModel'
            'ontology' | 'domainOntology' | 'choreographyOntology' |
            'choreographyModel' | 'sufficientSet'
role ::= 'initiatingParty'
            | 'answeringService'
            | 'correlatingService'
sufficientSet ::= 'SufficientSet (' name URI { entity } ')
formalism ::= 'Formalism (' nameFormalism { sufficientSet } ')
nameFormalism ::= 'MEPCConversational'
                    | 'FSM'
                    | 'logicBoxCorrespondence'
structure ::= 'Structure (' { formalism } ')
conversation ::= 'Conversation (' name URI { messageExchange } ')

```

⁷ The definition of the URI has been narrowed to better accommodate the requirements of the work.

```

messageExchange ::= 'MessageExchange ( ' name URI [ mep ] { message } )'
mep ::= 'mep ( ' name URI [ description ] )'
message ::= 'Message ( ' name URI [ from ] [ to ] { document } )'
from ::= party
to ::= party
document ::= 'Document ( ' name URI { element } )'
element ::= 'Element ( ' type name value )'
type ::= 'xs:string'
        | 'xs:decimal'
        | 'xs:integer'
        | 'xs:float'
        | 'xs:boolean'
        | 'xs:date'
        | 'xs:time'

value ::= valueSpace8
description ::= part
behavior ::= 'behavior ( { formalism } )'
choreography ::= 'Choreography ( ' name URI [ conversation ] { part } )'
part ::= 'Part ( ' name URI [ messageExchange ] { guardedTransition } )'
guardedTransition ::= 'GuardedTransition ( ' name URI { event
        [ guardedCondition ] {
        action } )'
guardedCondition ::= 'GuardedCondition ( ' name URI [ rule ] )'
rule ::= 'Rule ( if booleanExpression then state )'
event ::= 'Event ( ' name URI [ booleanExpression ] )'
booleanExpression ::= 'BooleanExpression ( ' name URI LogicalExpression )'
logicalExpression ::= expr9
action ::= 'Action ( ' name URI [ party ] [ message ] )'
state ::= 'State ( ' name URI { subState } )'
subState ::= 'SubState ( ' state )'
operation ::= 'Operation ( { formalism } )'
logicGroup ::= 'LogicGroup ( ' name URI [ conversation ] { logicDiagram } )'
logicDiagram ::= 'LogicDiagram ( ' name URI [ inputMessageExchange ]
        [ outputMessageExchange ]
        { logicBox } )'
logicBox ::= 'LogicBox ( ' name URI boxType { inputMessage
        [ inputMep ] [ outputMep ] [ ontologyMapping ] )'

correspondenceTable ::= 'correspondenceTable ( ' name URI
        { inputMessageExchange }
        { outputMessageExchange }
        value )'

```

⁸ XSD value-space for a given data type

⁹ WSMML expression as defined in [Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.]

```

correspondenceModel ::= 'correspondenceModel (' name URI
                        [ initatingPartyCorrespondenceTable ]
                        [ answeringServiceCorrespondenceTable ] ')'
boxType ::= 'refineBox' | 'mergeBox' | 'splitBox' | 'selectBox' | 'addBox'
inputMep ::= mep
outputMep ::= mep
inputMessageExchange ::= messageExchange
outputMessageExchange ::= messageExchange
initatingPartyCorrespondenceTable ::= correspondenceTable
answeringServiceCorrespondenceTable ::= correspondenceTable
semantics ::= 'Semantics (' { domainOntology } { choreographyOntology }
                [ choreographyMapping ] ')'
ontology ::= 'Ontology ('name URI ')
domainOntology ::= 'DomainOntology ('ontology ')
choreographyModel ::= 'ChoreographyModel (' ontology ')

choreographyOntology ::= 'ChoreographyOntology (' ontology ')
ontologyMapping ::= 'OntologyMapping ('name URI { source } { target } ')'
choreographyMapping ::= ontologyMapping
source ::= ontology | ontologyMapping
target ::= ontology
identifier ::= letter { letter | digit } | digit { letter | digit }
letter ::= 'a' | 'b' | 'c' | 'd' | 'e' | 'f' | 'g' | 'h' | 'i' | 'j' | 'k' | 'l' | 'm' | 'n' | 'o' | 'p' |
            'q' | 'r' | 's' | 't' | 'u' | 'v' | 'w' | 'x' | 'y' | 'z' | '_' | '-' | '.' | '/' | ':' | '@'
digit ::= '0' | '1' | '2' | '3' | '4' | '5' | '6' | '7' | '8' |

```

6 Use case: BT Wholesale KM Operational Support System

SOPHI E¹⁰ has provided the paradigm used to define the choreographies of the trading partners and BT as Wholesale Provider in the context of the DIP project¹¹. Using the previously defined domain ontology and the choreography ontology model, it is possible to specify a choreography that depicts the structural and behavioral models. To do so, it imports from both (domain and model choreography) ontologies.

Figure 2 shows the MEPs followed by both interacting parties. If the service provider were to use a different MEP and terminology than BT Wholesale, then the operational model of SOPHI E can be applied. In this case, the Service Provider uses the message exchange *tPontTestRequest* following the MEP *request-response* while BT Wholesale makes use of the message exchange *eCoTestRequest* following the *In-Multi-Out* one. More concretely, the Service provider starts the message exchange with the *MRequest* message, while BT Wholesale expects the message *testRequest*. Additionally, BT provides two different response message (*failure* and *success*),

¹⁰ The evaluation focuses at the message exchange level as it is considered enough to prove the consistency of the model. In later versions of the work, probably full conversations will be exemplified.

¹¹ <http://dip.semanticweb.org/>

indicating whether the test was accepted or rejected, and if accepted, the result of the test, while the *Service Provider* awaits the reception of a single message named *MCompleted* accounting for both of them.

Figure 2: Request-Response and In-Multi-Out Message Exchange Pattern

Elements	<i>testPerformer</i> (<i>testPerformerCustomerID</i> , <i>testPerformerPartyID</i>), <i>testConductor</i> (<i>testConductorAgencyID</i> , <i>testConductorPartyID</i>), <i>testReference</i> (<i>testIdentifier</i> , <i>testDate</i>), <i>testCategory</i> , <i>testParam1</i> , <i>testParam2</i> , ..., <i>testParamn</i> , <i>testResult1</i> , <i>testResult2</i> ,..., <i>testResultn</i> , <i>testOK</i>
Documents	<i>DRequest</i> , <i>DCompleted</i>
Messages	<i>MRequest</i> , <i>MCompleted</i>
Documents-Elements mapping	<i>DRequest</i> .{ <i>testPerformer</i> , <i>testConductor</i> , <i>testReference</i> , <i>testCategory</i> , <i>testParameters</i> } <i>DCompleted</i> .{ <i>testReference</i> , <i>testCategory</i> , <i>testOK</i> , <i>testResults</i> }
Messages-Documents mapping	<i>MRequest</i> .{ <i>DRequest</i> } <i>MCompleted</i> .{ <i>DCompleted</i> }

Table 6: Service Provider structural model

6.1 Structural Model

The service provider follows the message exchange pattern “*request-response*” based on the structural model¹² *tPontStr*, detailed in Table 6.

The test conductor follows the message exchange pattern “*in-multi-out*” which uses the structural model *eCoStr*, detailed in table 7.

Elements	<i>performer (customerID, performerPartyID), conductor (agencyID, conductorPartyID), reference (identifier,date), category, parameter1,parameter2, ..., parametern, result1, result2,...,resultn, accepted</i>
Documents	<i>requestDoc, successDoc, failureDoc</i>
Messages	<i>testRequest, failure, success</i>
Documents-Elements mapping	<i>requestDoc.{ performer, conductor, reference, category, parameters } successDoc.{ reference, category, accepted, results } failureDoc.{ reference, category, accepted }</i>
Messages-Documents mapping	<i>testRequest.{requestDoc } success.{ successDoc } failure.{ failureDoc }</i>

Table 7: *BT Wholesale structural model*

	Service Provider	BT Wholesale
Actions	<i>sendMRequest</i>	<i>outFailure, outSuccess</i>
Boolean Expressions	<i>receiveMCompleted</i>	<i>recTestRequest</i>

Table 8: *Behavioral model of both parties*

¹² With the aim of facilitating the reader understanding *testPerformer*, *testConductor*, *testReference* are presented at this point as complex data structure. However, as far as SOPHIE concerns they are single elements, built as a result of the concatenation of their constituents. The same principle applies to the elements *performer*, *conductor* and *reference* of the BT Wholesale structural model.

6.2 Behavioral Model

As far as the behavioral model concerns, Table 8 depicts the most relevant entities required to assert interoperability among the behavioral models *tPontBhv* and *eCoBhv*.

In [Arroyo, 07] the complete ontologies that describe the domain knowledge and choreographies of both parties are carefully depicted.

7 Conclusion and future work

This paper has presented the ontology and grammar of **SOPHIE**, an extensible knowledge management conceptual framework that is especially suitable for supporting the fine grained interaction among services following different structural, behavioral or semantic models. **SOPHIE** elaborates on current existing initiatives trying to rise above their limitations with the addition of a computational semantics and a clear separation of concerns that help to overcoming intrinsic service heterogeneity. On the one hand, the **SOPHIE** ontology allows to semantically describing the conversational patterns of interacting services, with the aim of, as a result of a reasoning task, producing the intermediate models that enable communication among heterogeneous parties in knowledge intensive settings. On the other hand, the clear separation of concerns facilitates to easily change, add or modify the different underlying formalisms, without impacting other concerns or the architecture itself.

The applicability of **SOPHIE** as semantic framework for the integration of choreographies has been demonstrated, as a solution to the compatibility of data and interchange details between parties engaged in business collaboration. **SOPHIE** can thus be considered an extension to existing languages and formalisms dealing with choreography that allows the reconciliation of divergences that are common in concrete implementation of typical scenarios. A detailed example of such capability centred in KM for the Telecommunications field.

The mapping provided in this paper can be further extended and revised for concrete application profiles, and it is essentially intended to provide a concrete realization of an existing ontology of KM [Holsapple04], thus sharing with it the objective of providing a foundation for systematic KM research study and practice.

Future work should deal with improving the abilities of the choreography service, by extending the different conceptual models with the addition of new formalisms remains open. Also, the definition of a mapping language that permits executing an operational model in traditional workflow engines represents an interesting research field. Areas of this work that definitely need to be researched are the assessment of performances, QoS and security, as the discussion about these topics is well out of the scope of this work. In addition to that, the extension to support different communication frameworks constitutes an interesting research area.

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References

- [Arroyo, 07] Arroyo, S (2007). SOPHIE: A choreography framework for semantic services. PhD Thesis.
- [Arroyo, 06] Arroyo, S., López Cobo, J.M. and Sicilia, M. (2006). Patterns of Message Interchange in Decoupled Hypermedia Systems. *Journal of Networks and Computer Applications*. 2006 (to appear).
- [Arroyo, 06] Arroyo, S., Duke, A., López-Cobo, J. M. and Sicilia, M. A. (2006). A Model-driven Choreography Conceptual Framework. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*. 2006 (to appear).
- [Booch, 99] Booch, G., Rumbaugh, J., and Jacobs, I.: “The Unified Modelling Language User Guide, Addison-Wesley, 1999.
- [de Bruijn, 04] de Bruijn, J. (editor), Polleres, A., Lara, Ruben, Fensel, D.: “D20.3 v0.1 OWL Flight” WSMO Working draft, <http://www.wsmo.org/2004/d20/d20.3/v0.1/20040823/>, 2004.
- [Fensel, 01] Fensel, D.: “Ontologies: Silver Bullet for Knowledge Management and Electronic Commerce”, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2001.
- [Gruber, 93] Gruber, T. R. (1993). A Translation Approach to Portable Ontology Specifications, *Knowledge Acquisition*, 5:199-220, 1993.
- [Holsapple, 04] C.W. Holsapple, K.D. Joshi, A formal knowledge management ontology: Conduct, activities, resources and influences, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* 55 (7) (2004) 593–612.
- [Maedche, 03] A. Maedche, B. Motik, L. Stojanovic, R. Studer, R. Volz, Ontologies for enterprise knowledge management, *IEEE Intelligent Systems* 18 (2) (2003) 26–33.
- [Marwick, 01] A.D. Marwick, Knowledge management technology, *IBM Systems Journal* 40 (4) (2001) 814–830.
- [Mohame, 04] A. Mohame, S. Lee, S. Salim, An ontology-based knowledge model for software experience management, *Journal of Knowledge Management Practice* 5 (2004).
- [Roman, 04] Roman, D., Scicluna, J., Feier, C., (eds.) Stollberg, M and Fensel, D.: “D14v0.1. Ontology-based Choreography and Orchestration of WSMO Services”, <http://www.wsmo.org/TR/d14/v0.1/>, March, 2005.
- [Roman, 04] Roman, D., Lausen, H. and Keller, U. (eds): *Web Service Modeling Ontology. WSMO Working Draft v0.3*. <http://www.wsmo.org/2004/d2/v1.0/>, 2004.
- [Sicilia, 06] Sicilia, M. A. Lytras, M., Rodríguez, E., García-Barriocanal. (2006). Integrating descriptions of knowledge management learning activities into large ontological structures: A case study. *Data & Knowledge Engineering* 57 (2006) 111–121.

[Wagner, 06] Wagner, F. (2006). Modeling Software with Finite State Machines: A Practical Approach", Auerbach Publications.